

EUPHRESCO II

Deliverables 3.1, 3.2, 3.3

Initiation of transnational research activities

First (DL3.1), second (DL 3.2) and third (DL3.3) round of topics and calls - Topics for all three rounds of trans-national calls/projects identified, together with funding mechanisms; calls (competitive and/or non-competitive) for proposals initiated.

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<http://www.euphresco.org>

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Summary

Within EUPHRESKO II three annual rounds of research initiation were established from 2011 to 2013. Partners (and one observer) participated in 179 research funding activities in 30 topics selected for funding. While WP3 of EUPHRESKO II, supported by the Project Management Group (PMG), arranged for the establishing of the initiation phases, the Topic Coordinators (TC) were responsible for the administrative efforts in the implementation phases. For the funding of topics the originally developed “pure” funding mechanisms non-competitive (NC), virtual common pot (VP), real common pot (RP) as well as a newly developed mixed funding mechanism (NC & VP) were applied. The recommendation from EUPHRESKO I to use funding mechanisms to provide more flexibility with regard to the need and potential for competition, i.e. topic dependent was realized by the development and successful use of a new mixed funding mechanism, despite starting problems due to the higher complexity of the process.

The EUPHRESKO I recommendation to improve the topic suggestion and topic selection process with regard to increased transparency and participation of all interested partners led to an iterative procedure of applying agreed eligible criteria subsequently to topic finding workshops for all 3 research rounds. While the more complex criteria were used for the evaluation of the topic suggestions by the topic reviewer in all research rounds, those criteria that were easier to be automated in an online procedure were included in the online processing tool for automatic selection on the EUPHRESKO website. The ERALEARN toolbox cycle phases for research call planning and implementation were implemented in EUPHRESKO II.

Overall the development and use of the newly developed online tools resulted in a facilitation of the process administration (see also DL3.4 for time requirements).

All EUPHRESKO-1 partner countries participated in at least 1 project as well as 84% of the new partners. 50% of the partner countries provided the 14 TCs for 30 funded topics. In total the amount of decided funds in all 3 research rounds accumulated to about 6.8 mill €. The top three primary topic areas covered with regard to crops were related to potatoes (& solanaceae), fruit crops and forestry, whereas the major secondary topic area was diagnostic methods.

As new collaboration mechanisms both regional and crop related workshops and topic related workshops were carried out successfully.

Consequently existing expertise and resources were used more efficiently and contributing higher quality research. The building of mutual trust and confidence in trans-national cooperation and collaboration and the network of funders and researchers was reinforced.

Introduction

Definition of terms

Funding Consortium (FC) – Consortium of funders of a specific topic/project (vs. 'CSC' as used in EUPHRESKO I which contained all funders of all topics together)

National Call Contact Point (NCCP) – Representatives of the funding organisations on the national level. Can but need not to be different from the contact person of the Funder(s) of a country

National funding organisation / (Call) Funder – EUPHRESKO partner (or observer) that supports (provide funds for) one (or more) EUPHRESKO projects

Partner / Observer – Project partner (or observer) of the ERA-Net Project EUPHRESKO II

PMG – EUPHRESKO II project management group

Project Coordinator (PC) (same as: 'Research consortium coordinator') Leader of a research consortium; responsible for the contact with the network and for the delivery of documents

Research Consortium (RC) – Consortium of research providers applying for a topic (applicants) by submitting a proposal/carrying out the tasks of an agreed project

Topic Coordinator (TC) - The TC is one network partner who took over the coordination of a topic in the topic selection phase. The principal role of the TC is to guarantee the lifeline between the research project and the EUPHRESKO network partners

WP1 / WP2 / WP3 / WP4 / WP 5 - EUPHRESKO II work package leaders and co-operators

ERA-Net EUPHRESKO

(This chapter was produced for EUPHRESKO II Modus Oparandi (March 2014))

The ERA-Net Project EUPHRESKO II is the continuance of EUPHRESKO, a policy-led coordination action, initiated by the EU Council Working Party of Chief Officers of Plant Health Services (COPHS). EUPHRESKO II started in January 2011, funded for 3 years from the EU 7th framework programme. EUPHRESKO stands for **European Phytosanitary Research Cooperation** and connects phytosanitary (statutory plant health) research funders (programme owners or managers) from 22 countries: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Portugal, Russia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and the UK.

The aim of the EUPHRESKO projects was to coordinate phytosanitary research at the European level. This involved coordination and co-operation between nationally-based phytosanitary research programmes in Europe for the first time through networking of research activities and a potential mutual opening or collaboration between national programmes. This coordination of national research has not been done significantly before EUPHRESKO nor has there been any significant trans-national funding of research, nor any alignment with EU-funded plant health research. EUPHRESKO therefore combines three main goals:

- Develop phytosanitary research policy and coordination at the EU-wide level.
- Optimise the research provision that underpins EU quarantine plant health policy development and implementation by reducing duplication and pooling resources.
- Increase the capacity of European phytosanitary science and research, in order to prevent the disappearance of expertise and maintain Europe's competitiveness in the global market. This supports EPPO's declaration of a *State of Emergency in Plant Health* in Madeira in 2004.

The projects were fully supported by the EU Council Working Party of Chief Officers for Plant Health Services (COPHS), The European Commission's Directorate General for Health and Consumer Protection (DG SANCO), the European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organisation (EPPO) and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), all of which have European plant health responsibilities.

One component of the work plan of EUPHRESKO and EUPHRESKO II was the establishment of a self-sustainable, long-term cooperation network in Europe to ensure a durable coordination of European phytosanitary research. The initial basis for such a cooperation initiative has already been established through EUPHRESKO's activities since 2006.

Work package 3

(This chapter was produced for EUPHRESKO II project description and copied without changes.)

Objectives:

This work-package aims to deepen the European Plant Health Research network cooperation by delivering new transnational research activities, especially coordinated or jointly-funded research projects. These will further support the development and implementation of Plant Health Policy and improve the phytosanitary science base in Europe. Such joint research activities will build additional confidence and experience in joint transnational research commissioning and demonstrate the added value and benefits that result. Research projects that move beyond being pilots are envisaged and which provide customised answers responsively to specific problems relating to both quarantine (regulated) and emerging pests of phytosanitary concern. The work will consolidate and build on the success of previous activities and establish a regular routine and culture of collaboration. The main specific objectives are:

- To identify, prioritise and select trans-national research topics suitable for cooperation and collaboration, especially jointly-funded projects, including consultation with current key stakeholders and advisors
- To initiate trans-national research collaborations to support EU plant health policy, operations and science capability.

Description of work and role of partners:

This work-package will aim to deepen the trans-national research activities started in EUPHRESKO-I by initiating plant health policy-driven research collaborations of longer duration, of a wider scope and with more budget than the pilot projects following a regular, annual cycle. Both experienced and possibly new mechanisms and processes, which have possibly been developed in WP4, such as emergency track procedures of funding and collaboration will be applied. Regional, international or sector-based topics from WP5 will also be fed in to WP3; new partners will also be integrated into WP3 activities (see WP5).

3.1. Identify, prioritise and select topics and mechanisms for trans-national research activities

- Identify topics, potential funds and/or resources and the funding mechanism for individual trans-national coordination or joint commissioning on an annual basis, i.e. to operate the phytosanitary market place where mutual research needs are identified and prioritised and trans-national research initiated to better/directly address them.
- The prioritisation of topics identified as appropriate for trans-national research will involve the national funders and other stakeholders important to identifying research needs/priorities (agenda setting) (e.g. EPPO, EFSA, DG-SANCO and its SCPH, including the recently re-established Annexes Working Group) to ensure this is fully policy led. For prioritising research activities suitable for transnational cooperation, a key criterion will be the need for

research that provides quick and tailored answers to urgent policy problems related to current or emerging plant health pest problems of statutory significance.

- Topic selection will also account for research being funded at the EU level, e.g. by the EU's Framework Programmes. Where appropriate, trans-national research initiated via EUPHRESKO-II will seek to complement or build on previous or on-going EU-funded research projects ensuring added value for both EU and national funds. Whereas EU-funded research projects tend to be primarily larger and/or more strategic projects (e.g. PRATIQUE, developing pest risk analysis science; QBOL, developing DNA barcoding approaches in support of EU-wide diagnostics; Q-DETECT, developing pest detection tools for inspection services), trans-national projects will tend to be more applied, short to mid-term projects, and typically more regionally-based and of immediate concern.
- The choice of the coordination and funding mechanisms for such trans-national research will be made according to the specific topic and the policy, operational or science need, e.g. the competitive funding routes (virtual common pot or real common pot) or non-competitive funding routes (e.g. direct non-competitive commissioning via single collaborative projects, or clustering of national projects on similar issues to prevent duplication and ensure outputs provide European added value and meet the wider European context and EU policy, operational and science needs) trialled in EUPHRESKO-I.
- Where appropriate though, new ways and means of cooperating and collaborating could be applied, e.g. mixed funding mechanisms, fellowship schemes, clustering as a means of linking national projects, opportunities to link to other funding sources (e.g. Marie Curie) partly based on or in parallel with the approaches developed in WP4.

3.2. Implement joint research activities

- For each selected research topic, individual funding consortia will be formed. Topic and call responsibilities will be assigned individually within each funding consortium. Topic descriptions and specifications will be produced and finalised according to the agreed responsibilities. Funds and/or resources for the respective research activities will be confirmed and collaboration agreements (e.g. letters of commitment as in EUPHRESKO-I) will formalise the funding collaborations and initiate the call or commissioning processes by the funding consortium. All EUPHRESKO-II partners commit themselves to contributing resources to at least one joint trans-national research activity. As appropriate, call secretariat processes will be established for each topic.
- For the implementation of the joint research activities we expect the total level of national funds deployed annually to trans-national projects to be at least similar to that committed in the previous EUPHRESKO pilot projects in 2008.
- Projects will move beyond just the pilot projects done within EUPHRESKO-I (since pilots impose certain constraints, e.g. the need to evaluate mechanisms and processes within the EUPHRESKO ERA-Net's timescales). Project length and size, and funding mechanism, will be primarily determined by the topic, the policy need and the available funds

Deliverables of WP3

D3.1) First round of topics and calls: Topics for first round of trans-national calls/projects identified, together with funding mechanisms; calls (competitive and/or non-competitive) for proposals initiated. [month 13]

D3.2) Second round of topics and calls: Topics for second round of trans-national calls/projects identified, together with funding mechanisms; calls (competitive and/or non-competitive) for proposals initiated. [month 25]

D3.3) Third round of topics: Topics for third annual round of trans-national calls/projects identified, together with funding mechanisms. [month 34]

D3.4) Time inputs for activities: Times and inputs required for activities available for all three project rounds recorded and analysed. [month 38]

Transnational research initiation activities – Timing & Procedure	2011	2012	2013
<i>Research initiation phases</i>			
Preparation of Initiation	Jan – Mar 2011	Feb – Mar 2012	Jan – Feb 2013
Initial identification of topic suggestions	Mar 2011	Mar - Jun 2012	Feb - Apr 2013
Merge of topic suggestions (<i>separate phase since 2013 Round</i>)			Mai 2013
Joining listed Topic suggestions	Apr 2011	Jun 2012	Jun 2013
Initial identification – Information on funders & funds (<i>phase only 2011 in timetable</i>)	Apr 2011		
Establishment of Long List of Topics	May 2011	Jul 2012	Jul 2013
Topic Coordinator (TC) assignment	May - Jun 2011	Aug 2012	Jul - Aug 2013
Production of (short) topic description	Jun - Aug 2011	Aug - Oct 2012	Sep - Oct 2013
Prioritization of topic choice	Aug - Sep 2011		
Decision & Agreement on Final Topic List	Sep(-Oct) 2011		
Production of document templates & spread with Final Topic List	Oct 2011		
<i>Latest steps replaced in 2012 & 2013 by:</i> Funding decision phase / Establishment of Funding Consortia (FC)		Nov - Dec 2012	Nov 2013 – Jan 2014
<i>END of WP3's responsibility - START of Funding Consortia's responsibility (WP3 to support)</i>			
Agreement phase	see below		
Production and signing of commitments	see below		
<u>Research implementation - non – competitive:</u> Project management installation & Monitoring of execution and result dissemination	Timing/deadlines to be decided by		
<u>Research implementation – competitive topics:</u> Call preannouncement / preparation & Call execution & Proposal evaluation, decision, project commissioning & Monitoring of execution and result dissemination	Funding Consortia topic by topic		

Details of phases for transnational research initiation activities

(Information in this chapter is provided as within the online timetable.)

Research Initiation

Preparation of Initiation

WHO: PMG, WP3

WHAT: Decisions on timetable, criteria*, etc.

Initial identification of topic suggestions

WHO: Partner, Observer, Advisor, (Reviewer)

WHAT:

(1) Partner, Observer collect topic suggestions in compliance with topic suggestion criteria* nationally and provide them via the web-tool

(2) Reviewer provide specific comments on compliance with topic suggestion criteria

(3) Partner, Observer, Advisor provide comments on technical content of suggested topics (in case of available information, even if no interest in funding)

(4) Partner, Observer join given topic suggestions (in case of funding interest) (Note: This is the first possibility to join given topic suggestions!)

RESULT at deadline: All topics of interest are suggested (Note: after this phase no new topic suggestions for this round of research initiation are possible!)

Merge of topic suggestions

WHO: Reviewer, Partner, Observer

WHAT:

(1) Reviewer check the topic suggestions for double entries or topics with overlaps/close relations and provide Partner, Observer with suggestions for potential topic merges

(2) Partner, Observer provide their objections against the suggestions

RESULT at deadline: Topics that were entered more than one time or that are quite close to others are merged (unless objections are given)

Joining listed Topic suggestions

WHO: Partner, Observer, Advisor

WHAT:

(1) Partner, Observer with potential funding interest in the topic JOIN the topic (=> Contributors)

(2) Partner, Observer, Advisor comment on given topic suggestions (as above)

RESULT at deadline: Interest in topic(s) indicated by Partner, Observer (potential funders); topic suggestions completed/amended through comments from Partner, Observer, Advisor

Establishment of Long List of Topics

WHO: Reviewer

WHAT: Provide comments on topic suggestions (and select according to criteria)

RESULT: List of topic suggestions in compliance with selection criteria, supported with Reviewer comments

Note: AUTOMATIC drop out of topic suggestions not fitting the concerning criteria! (Enough interest)

Topic Coordinator (TC) assignment

WHO: Contributors (potential Funder therefore Partner, Observer interested in funding a topic)

WHAT:

(1) Contributors discuss and decide who (of them) will take over the Topic Coordinator (TC) tasks*

(2) The resulting Partner assign himself via the web-tool as Topic Coordinator (TC)

RESULT at deadline: Topics with Topic Coordinator listed

Note: AUTOMATIC drop out of topic suggestions not fitting the concerning criteria! (Enough interest, assigned TC)

Production of (short) topic description

WHO: Topic Coordinator (TC); Contributors (Partner, Observer) of the topic

WHAT:

TC to initiation STD production and coordinate input from Partner, Observer; this could also include a meeting of these potential funders (maybe virtually);

TC is responsible for on time upload (/spread) of the agreed final STD-version before the deadline;

NOTE: the agreed funding mechanism needs to be provided and the request on 'if an open call will get established' needs to get answered by the TC!

RESULT at deadline: Topics of interest have a short topic description (STD) uploaded; Funding mechanisms outlined

Note: AUTOMATIC drop out of topic suggestions not fitting the concerning criteria! (Enough interest, assigned Topic Coordinator (TC), uploaded short topic description (STD))

Funding decision phase / Establishment of Funding Consortia (FC)

WHO: ALL potential Funder (even those not being involved in the topic establishment before; Partner, Observer); Reviewer

WHAT:

(!) Funders DECIDE - based on the short topic description (STD) - on their participation as Funder of the respective topic(s);

(-) TC enters Partners, Observers now interested in topics where they are not listed as contributors yet, via the web tool (otherwise they are not able to provide their funding decision!)

(-) Funders provide their decisions via the web-tool (including the decided funds (€!))

RESULT: Funding Consortia (FC) of topics established

END of WP3's responsibility - START of Funding Consortia's responsibility (WP3 to support)

all further end dates/deadlines are to be decided by FC per topic

Agreement phase [*Agreement-phase and commitment signing-phase might have smooth transition (in timing and content)*]

WHO: Funding Consortium(FC) led by TC

WHAT:

FC's discuss and decide on all administrative and management issues (e.g. splitting of tasks; documents* in use; evaluation issues; financial issues (transfer of funds, mechanism); timing, ...); (for different comp. topics FC's can decide to coordinate the establishing of an EUPHRESKO call and coordinate all related issues together)

RESULT: Decisions on all issues related to the topic/the resulting project are carried out by the concerning FC

Production and signing of commitments

WHO: Funding Consortium (FC) led by TC

WHAT:

(1) Amend the selected agreement and commitment documents (e.g. Common contract conditions, Call principles, LoC, etc.), which include the final version of the topic description, in accordance with the decisions of the 'Agreement phase' *

(2) Spread, sign and collect the documents

RESULT: Agreed documents for the respective topic are signed

(NOTE that PMG has decided that it is not a requirement that all LoI's/LoC's are collected before the start of a NC project)

Research implementation - non – competitive:

Project management installation

WHO: Funding Consortia (FC) with Topic Coordinator (TC) and Research Consortia (RC) with Project Coordinator (PC)

WHAT:

Project management installation (PC assignment, provision of information on the participating researchers, national commitment signing ...); production and evaluation of work plan/proposal ...

RESULT: Agreed Research Consortium - led by a Project Coordinator - given; all necessary agreements amended, signed and collected; work plan confirmed

*followed by **Monitoring of project execution and result dissemination** (details not predetermined in the online timetable)*

Research implementation – competitive topics:

Call preannouncement / preparation

WHO: Website provider, FC/TC, National Funder (NCCP's)

WHAT:

Provision and spread of information on the upcoming call (call text, dates,...); amendment and upload of necessary documents for the application procedure; amendment of documents for the proposal evaluation and decision procedure; etc.*

RESULT: potentially interested researchers are informed; required documents are prepared

Call execution

WHO: Website provider; FC/TC, Applicants (Research Consortia (RC) with Project Coordinator (PC))

WHAT:

Applicants submit proposals; helpdesk/support will be provided

RESULT: one/more proposals per topic submitted via Project Coordinators

Proposal evaluation, decision, project commissioning

WHO: FC/TC, scientific peer reviewer, RC

WHAT: (details for below step depending on the agreed procedure of the concerning FC)

- (1) Evaluation of the project proposal(s) (no standard procedure, few tools* in tool book available);
- (2) Decision on the project proposal(s)
- (3) Project commissioning (production, spread and signing of commitments)

RESULT: FC decision on the submitted proposals, proposals amended (if necessary); commitments signed with RC of successful proposal(s)

*followed by **Monitoring of project execution and result dissemination** (details not predetermined in the online timetable)*

Figure 1 - EUPHRESKO II - Research Initiation & Implementation phases

Notes and experiences of WP3 (initiator and topic reviewer)

Preparation of initiation

All three annual rounds of research initiation required considerable preparation from the initiator of the rounds and support from the Project Management Group (PMG) (for discussion and decisions) in the first months of every project year.

The **timetable**, i.e. the development and timing of all phases in the process, and the establishing of the topic suggestion and selection **criteria** were the main issues to tackle in this phase. These tasks were mainly established by adapting the tool book templates from EUPHRESKO I at the start of the 2011 round. The templates for activity charts and guidelines that were established in EUPHRESKO I with the intention of supporting a call secretariat were adapted to the actual situation in which WP3 served as initiator and topic suggestion reviewer until a certain point in the process from which on the funders (FC) took over the responsibility for their topics. To allow old (EUPHRESKO I+II) and especially new (only EUPHRESKO II) project partners and observers to better understand the process and timing of the phases **activity charts** and **guidelines** for the different funding mechanisms were established or adapted in 2011 and improved in the subsequent years.

During the “learning by doing” process throughout EUPHRESKO II specific research round phases were also changed/replaced/added according to the experiences of the previous rounds (see differences of the rounds in the overview table). This also resulted in different

documents that were provided on the website, especially the **short timetable** (with the possibility of extension to receive details) which was supported by a separate **FAQ** document and a so called '**authorisation matrix**'. These online documents allowed new partners to take part in the process even at their first participation. Furthermore, the online timetable tool was installed in a way that enabled the initiator to **open a new initiation round** without the support of the IT service, including setting the timing for the different phases and activating automatic **reminders** for various phases.

While automatic reminder e-mails were available and steered by the settings in the timetable no automatic **mail** system was developed for the **start and end of the individual phases**. This task turned out to be significant for WP3 who informed the partners, observers and advisors about the upcoming issues at the start of the individual phases and about the results at the end of the same.

Initial identification of topic suggestions

Project participants were asked beforehand to nationally collect suggestions for topics in workshops or by the use of questionnaires. In all three rounds the annual EUPHRESKO project **meeting** in spring was used by the partners as platform for an initial discussion on topic suggestions for the upcoming round. **Workshops** were arranged at the meeting and the results were collected and provided in a condensed version afterwards. However only in 2011 the results were used directly as topic suggestions, whereas in 2012 and 2013 the workshop outcome was provided as a separate document to the partners who then were asked to again provide the topic suggestions relevant for them. Next to the reduced workload for the initiator the later model had the positive effect that those partners with the highest interest in a topic took over the lead for this topic in the suggestion phase, took care for the provision and inclusion of important and detailed information and in some cases took over the TC tasks later in the process.

While in 2011 for this phase basically a 'Google **spread sheet**' was in use (with moderate success due to different login problems), this was one of the first phases that was technically supported by newly developed **online** tools. A first version that allowed providing topic suggestions online was already available in 2012 and in an improved version in the 2013 round.

Merge of topic suggestions

The problem of overlapping topics first rose in 2012 and required separate activities which at that time were carried out within an adjacent phase. In 2013 a separate phase was added to the timetable. Along with this, with the development and later on improvement of the online tool, the initiator/reviewer was supported with the possibility to merge one topic into another within the online system. While this still required a separate email request to the partners for potential objections it allowed the reviewer, after analysing the objections, as a result to merge topics directly rather than deleting and re-entering them to the system.

Joining listed Topic suggestions

To allow the partners and observers to provide information on their potential interest in funding a specific topic an excel questionnaire was used in 2011 while from 2012 on the

online tool allowed all partners and observers (with member accounts) to directly enter themselves at the topic of interest. This included the provision of basic information on the preferred project timing, funding mechanism and participation as Topic Coordinator (TC).

In the 2012 and 2013 version of the online tool the possibility to enter topics themselves ended for the partners and observers at the end of this phase. Later contributions could only be entered by the reviewer (with IT-service support), which caused delays.

Initial identification – Information on funders & funds

While the activities of this phase were carried out in all three years in EUPHRESKO II, the process phase was discarded from the timetable after 2011 because of too **few replies and delays** of returned information by the partners. To fulfill the task of collecting initial information on the potential funding interest of the partners irrespective of the finally selected topics a questionnaire from EUPHRESKO I was adapted. The returned questionnaires were analysed and the results provided to the partners.

Establishment of Long List of Topics

This first (of three) topic selection phases required activities of the reviewer (and the online system) only. On the basis of the topic list given at the end of the phase *joining listed topic suggestions* topics with too few support (1st selection criterion) were **dropped**. This was done manually in 2011 by the reviewer who established a document called 'Longlist' using only the remaining topics; also manually by the reviewer in 2012 via dropping topics with too few support from the online table of topic suggestions (drop button); automatically by the improved online system in 2013 which at the deadline of this phase dropped all topics not fulfilling the drop out criterion.

While a so called '**parking list**' was used in 2011 to collect the topics that were dropped but considered as important and therefore kept for potential later use a separate '**dropped topics**' tool was installed on the website and collected the topics of 2012 and 2013. This tool received improvements in 2013 and finally allowed also to **reactive** topics (during the *Initial identification of topic suggestions* phase of a subsequent round) and to **undo** the dropping (reviewer only) to avoid losing a topic for the actual round due to missing a deadline. Furthermore the reviewer was provided with the possibility to ultimately **delete** topics.

In 2013 for all **automatic dropping** phases an automatic information **e-mail system** was installed that informed the reviewer after the dropping about the important topic details and asks to check the executed dropping. The mail system, in combination with the possibilities described above (e.g. undo) allowed to apply the necessary **flexibility** which otherwise would only be given if these steps were carried out manually.

The second and maybe even more important task in this phase was the **provision of reviewer comments** for all remaining topics. Next to the basic information like listings of pests in EU regulations or EPPO lists more detailed information on projects financed from other sources with potential overlaps and/or synergies were provided by the WP3 leader. While in 2011 this information was added to the **Longlist** file, from 2012 onwards a separate space for reviewer comments at the individual topic window collected these valuable information.

While **dropping** and provision of reviewer **comments** was directly connected in 2011, it was split in two different steps when the **online tool** was developed. In the 2013 version the automatic dropping of topics applied after the provision of the reviewer comments. This causes potentially unnecessary work for the reviewer (providing comments for topics that will get dropped afterwards anyway) and should be suggested to get **swapped** in future.

TC Assignment

The Topic Coordinator assignment was arranged manually in **2011**. The **Longlist** of topics was spread for this issue and partners willing to take over the TC tasks were asked to provide this information. TC-assignment was again carried out manually in **2012** with the difference to the previous year that partners already had to provide indications on their potential willingness to take over the TC tasks when they joined the topic of interest. The then used approach was to **automatically assign** the partners with potential willingness as TC's in the case that only one partner indicated the willingness. For topics with more than one indication the relevant partners were contacted to find a solution. As this approach does not require active approval of the partners to take over the TC function, some partners were confused as they were suddenly assigned as TC's for several topics. To avoid this problem in **2013** the (newly available) online tool for this phase required **active participation** of the partners who needed to assign themselves (as TC's) on the website for the concerned topic. The latest approach resulted in a satisfactory reduction of the number of topic suggestions per TC and an adequate status of information about the required tasks by the TC's.

As the TC was seen as leading person for the topic in all subsequent phases, the availability of a TC was used as 2nd topic selection criterion. Therefore only topics with assigned TC remained in the process whereas topics without TC were dropped (manually or automatically by the online system).

Production of (short) topic description

The short topic descriptions (STD) were seen as the basis for the later funding decision and therefore only topics with provided STD remained in the process (3rd selection criterion) while the other topics were dropped (manually or by the online system).

After the TC's, together with all interested partners, had established the document for their topic they provided the STD to the network which was done via the reviewer in 2011 and directly via the online system from 2012 on (start of possibility to **upload documents** and **mark** documents as **final STD versions**.)

Due to the number of suggested topics the reviewer provided the partners and observers in 2011 and 2012 with a separate document that compiled all provided final STD's (**'collection of short topic descriptions'**).

In 2013 the upload function was improved in the way that TC's were also asked to provide information on the scheduled **funding route** of the topic (open EUPHRESKO call or not), as this information was not gathered before.

Decision phase

After the topics of the round had been selected (by the use of the above mentioned three iterative selection criteria) the partners were asked to finally decide on their participation in the topics. This was carried out in different ways in the three rounds.

In **2011** this phase was **split** in a **phase of prioritizing** topics by the partners followed by a separate **decision** and **agreement** phase which again was followed by a separate phase in which the final topic list was spread along with potentially required document templates. However, it turned out that the required prioritization documents were not easy to understand for some partners and that the approach of using the acceptable funding mechanism as main criterion for the final topic selection were not satisfactory.

To overcome these problems WP3 excluded the funding mechanism from the decision tools in the 2012 round, with the intention that the Funding Consortia (FC) decided on the funding mechanisms afterwards. This, together with the possibility to use mixed mechanisms, resulted in a feasible approach for the decision phase. As in the first round also in 2012 partners and observers were **provided with excel tables** containing the topic suggestions and were requested to enter **their final funding decisions** (including funds and potential alternative topics in case they finally would end up as the only funder for a topic). WP3 collected and compiled the information and circulated the final topic list along with potentially required document templates for the subsequent phases.

The improved online tool allowed operating the **decision phase** in **2013** already **online**. Partners used their accounts to **provide their positive funding decisions** (including information on funds) directly at the topic window resulting in a list of funders in a separate 'Funding Consortiums' box that also provided the total decided funds for the topic.

While the system overall worked well a recommendation for improvement of the tool for the decision phase would be to provide the possibility for **partners to join topics by themselves** also in this phase. This applies for partners that were not interested in the topic in the phases before and therefore were not given **as contributors** at the start of the decision phase. This caused extensive work for WP3 and the IT service to enter these newly interested partners as contributors so that they were able to enter their positive funding decisions afterwards (Only partners that are given as contributors at a topic (after they have joined it) have the possibility to enter a positive funding decision).

Recommendations on duration and improvements

From the experience of the 3 rounds it is important to note that for the phases that included the group of the partners and observers (versus only a smaller group of actors like PMG) at **minimum** one month was required and therefore the duration should be extended to at least two month in the case of including a period of extensive holidays (e.g. Jul/Aug and Dec/Jan). Furthermore especially the phase's *initial identification of topic suggestions*, *production of short topic descriptions* and the *Funding decision phase* need to have a significant duration to allow all partners to actively participate – which resulted in a two to three month duration in the latest timetable version for each of these phases.

As with the 2013 version of the online tool still **no possibility of a status update on the topics**, and later on, on the projects was available the network required separate manual requests on the topic/project status. This could be avoided with 'status of topic/project' boxes in the online tool and the provision of automatic status requests to the TC on a regular basis (once or twice a year).

The **timing and duration of the individual phases** changed in the different years and finally resulted in the timetable of the 2013 round which basically included most improved processes that caused delays in the previous rounds. For all phases besides the decision phase, problems with delays could be avoided in the last round, after establishing strict regulations to keep to deadlines and providing automatic reminder mails. However, due to the different requirements of the partners, it was not possible to set a satisfactory deadline for the **funding decision phase** resulting in a one month delay by the end of the initiation part of the 2013 round.

Comparison of ERA Learn and EUPHRESKO cycles

Figure 2 - Comparison of ERA Learn implementation cycle and EUPHRESKO research initiation phases

Please note that in EUPHRESKO II the three research initiation rounds were established on annual basis resulting in a twelve month period for the central organised activities.

Figure 3 - Combined graph of ERA learn cycle (blue) and EUPHRESKO initiation and implementation phases

Transnational research initiation activities – Results

Please note that the sources for the results outlined in this chapter are the final topic lists of the rounds. Please also be aware of the project status update information (see attachment).

Year of round	2011	2012	2013	Total
Number of topics	10	17	3	30
Used mechanisms (scheduled)	NC, Mixed NC/VP	NC, Mixed NC/VP, VP, RP	<i>(Expected: NC, pot. Mixed)</i>	<i>All available</i>
No. of these topics using the non-competitive route	6	10	3	19
No. of these topics using competition (RP/VP/mixed mechanism)	4	7	0	11
Number of partner/observer involved (participation in topic-funding)	21 partner 1 observer	21 partner 1 observer	11 partner	26 of 31 partner 1 of 12 obs.
Number of countries involved	17	17	9	21 of 22 partner countries + 1 obs.
Number of total funding activities (research participation)	81	81	17	179
Total amount of decided funds	2.708.607 €	3.607.300 €	523.000 €	6.838.907€
Number of Topic Coordinators	6	8	3	<i>14 diff. persons/ organisations</i>

Table 2 - EUPHRESKO II - Results of three rounds transnational research initiation activities

- 5 EUPHRESKO II partner did not have any funding activities (BE-FPS, CZ-MZe, FR-INRA, GR-BPI, UK-FR)
- 2 EUPHRESKO II partner countries did not have any funding activities of any of their partner organizations (CZ, GR)

Figure 4 – EUPHRESKO II - Participation in transnational research activities per partner country (€)

Figure 5 – EUPHRESKO II – Research participation and topic coordination’s per partner country

Figure 6 - EUPHRESKO II – Funded topics per (primary and secondary) topic area

Figure 7 - EUPHRESCO I & II - Total amount of decided funds per round

Figure 8 - EUPHRESCO II - Funded topics per funding mechanism (%)

2011 Round of Research Initiation

01-CEP

Current and emerging phytophthoras: research supporting risk assessment and risk management

Topic Coordinator: Alan Inman (Alan.Inman@defra.gsi.gov.uk)

02-PCN (Potato Cyst Nematode)

Use of novel molecular methods to understand population diversity and its implications on disease management through the use of resistant potato varieties

Topic Coordinator: Alex Reid (alex.reid@sasa.gsi.gov.uk)

03-MELOID

Development and validation of innovative diagnostic tools for detection and identification of Meloidogyne enterolobii in support of integrated plant protection strategies

Topic Coordinator: Gabriele Schachermayr (gabriele.schachermayr@blw.admin.ch)

04-SENDO

Diagnostic methods for Synchytrium endobioticum, especially for pathotype identification (SENDO)

Topic Coordinator: Alan Inman (Alan.Inman@defra.gsi.gov.uk)

05-DEP2

Assessment of the risk posed by ornamentals and tomato seeds infected by Pospiviroids to tomato crops and evaluation of Pospiviroid detection protocols for seed testing in tomato

Topic Coordinator: Thibaut Olivier (t.olivier@cra.wallonie.be)

06-PHYLIB

Epidemiology and diagnosis of potato phytoplasmas and Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum and their contribution to risk management

Topic Coordinator: David Kenyon (david.kenyon@sasa.gsi.gov.uk)

07-GRAFDEPI

Epidemiological studies on reservoir hosts and potential vectors of Grapevine flavescence dorée (GFD) and validation of different diagnostic procedures for GFD

Topic Coordinator: Sylvia Bluemel (sbluemel@ages.at)

08-APOPHYT

Evaluation of factors determining distribution, impact, detection and characterization of apple proliferation and other fruit tree phytoplasmoses in the European Community

Topic Coordinator: Silke Steinmüller (silke.steinmoeller@jki.bund.de)

09-PHYTFIRE

Phytosanitary diagnostic, on-site detection and epidemiology tools for fire blight

Topic Coordinator: Sylvia Bluemel (sbluemel@ages.at)

10-DROSKII

Damage potential of Drosophila suzukii and development of phytosanitary measures

Topic Coordinator: Silke Steinmüller (silke.steinmoeller@jki.bund.de)

Table 3 - EUPHRESKO II – Participation of partners in 2011 round of research initiation

Partner no.	Partner short name	Total Funds	Total activities
2	AT-BMLFUW	150.000 €	3
3	AT-AGES	50.000 €	5
5	BE-CRA-W	22.000 €	3
6	BE-EV ILVO	225.000 €	8
10	EE-MARDD	7.000 €	1
11	FI-MMM	140.000 €	1
14	DE-BLE	100.000 €	3
15	DE-JKI	10.000 €	4
17	IE-DAFF	37.200 €	2
18	IT-MiPAAF	300.000 €	6
19	IT-CRA	0 €	6
20	LT-MoA	75.000 €	3
22	NL-PPS	90.000 €	5
23	PT-INRB	60.000 €	3
25	ES-INIA	400.000 €	3
26	CH-FOAG	380.000 €	5
27	TR-MARA-GDAR	60.000 €	4
1	UK-DEFRA/FERA	415.407 €	5
29	UK-SASA	126.500 €	4
30	UA-IPP UAAS	13.500 €	3
31	RU-FGU VNIKR	20.000 €	2
Observer			
	Norway (Bioforsk)	27.000 €	2
	Funds totally decided:	2.708.607 €	
	Funding activities		81

2012 Round of Research Initiation

2 - ANOPLORISK (extension of existing EUPHRESKO project)

(Risk management and improvement of detection & identification tools for the EC listed Anoplophora species, A. chinensis and A. glabripennis)

Topic Coordinator: **DE-JKI**; Silke Steinmoeller; silke.steinmoeller@jki.bund.de

3 - Bursaphelenchus xylophilus methods for early detection

Topic Coordinator: **FR-DGAL** (repres. by ANSES); Géraldine Anthoine; geraldine.anthoine@anses.fr

5 - Clavibacter michiganensis ssp. sepedonicus

(The effects of disinfection on Clavibacter michiganensis subsp. sepedonicus and other bacterial pathogens of potato in Europe)

Topic Coordinator: **NL-NVWA**; Jan Schans; j.schans@minlnv.nl

8 - Determination of specificity and test performance study of current and novel molecular methods for **brown rot of potatoes** and identification of methods allowing for detection of non-European strains of brown rot

(Determination of specificity and test performance study of current and novel molecular methods for Ralstonia solanacearum (brown rot of potatoes) and identification of methods allowing for detection of non-European strains of brown rot)

Topic Coordinator: **NL-NVWA**; Jan Schans; j.schans@minlnv.nl

10 - Diagnostic assay for plant health threats in **wood chips** for bio-energy imported from other continents

(Diagnostics and risk management for plant health threats in wood chips and bark for bio-energy imported from other continents)

Topic Coordinator: **DK-DASTI**; Steen Lykke Nielsen; SteenL.Nielsen@agrsci.dk

11 - Dickeya and Pectobacterium on potatoes, bulbs and ornamentals

(Assessment of Dickeya and Pectobacterium spp. on potatoes and ornamentals)

Topic Coordinator: **NL-NVWA**; Jan Schans; j.schans@minlnv.nl

13 - Epitrix species, monitoring and detection methods.

(Epitrix (flea beetle) species, life cycles and detection method)

Topic Coordinator: **DK-DASTI**; Steen Lykke Nielsen; SteenL.Nielsen@agrsci.dk

16 - Grapevine flavescence doreé (FD) follow up Vitisens and GRAFDEPI

(Grapevine flavescence doreé (FD) follow up Vitisens, GRAFDEPI and Qdetect)

Topic Coordinator: **SI-MAE** Jana Erjavec; Jana.Erjavec@gov.si)

19 - Monochamus spp., insect vectors of Bursaphelenchus xylophilus

Topic Coordinator: **DK-DASTI**; Steen Lykke Nielsen; SteenL.Nielsen@agrsci.dk

24 - Plant Health Fellowship Programme/Scheme
(*Plant health fellowships*)

Topic Coordinator: **UK-DEFRA**; Alan Inman; Alan.Inman@defra.gsi.gov.uk

25 - Plant Sentinel Network

(*Establishing the basis for an International Plant Sentinel Network as an early-warning system for future pest threats.*)

Topic Coordinator: **UK-DEFRA**; Alan Inman; Alan.Inman@defra.gsi.gov.uk

26 - Population dynamics of *Meloidogyne chitwoodi* and *M. fallax*

Topic Coordinator: **NL-NVWA**; Jan Schans; j.schans@minlnv.nl

28 - *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *actinidiae* (bacterial canker of kiwifruit)
(*Development and harmonization of methods for diagnosis, detection and identification of *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *actinidiae*.*)

Topic Coordinator: **IT-MIPAAF**; Alberto Masci; a.masci@mpaaf.gov.it

29 - Reference collection for regulated viruses and viroids

Topic Coordinator: **NL-NVWA**; Jan Schans; j.schans@minlnv.nl

33 - Strawberry

(*Assessment and testing of strawberry pathogens*)

Topic Coordinator: **EE-MARDD**; Külli Kaare; kylli.kaare@agri.ee

36 - Validation of QBOL DNA-Barcoding Protocols
(*Validation of QBOL Barcoding protocols by end-users*)

Topic Coordinator: **UK-DEFRA**; Alan Inman; Alan.Inman@defra.gsi.gov.uk

37 - *Xanthomonas arboricola* pv. *pruni*

(*Rapid diagnostics of *Xanthomonas arboricola* pv. *pruni* (Xap): development and validation of methodologies for discrimination between Xap isolates and look-a-likes*)

Topic Coordinator: **NL-NVWA**; Jan Schans; j.schans@minlnv.nl

Table 4 - EUPHRESKO II – Participation of partners in 2012 round of research initiation

Partner no.	Partner short name	Total Funds	Total activities
2	AT-BMLFUW	150.000 €	4
3	AT-AGES	15.000 €	5
6	BE-EV ILVO	154.000 €	6
7	BG-AA	13.000 €	2
9	DK-DASTI	500.000 €	3
10	EE-EVPM	64.000 €	1
12	FR-DGAL	170.000 €	6
14	DE-BLE	100.000 €	2
15	DE-JKI	14.000 €	4
17	IE-DAFM	10.700 €	1
18	IT-MIPAAF	0 €	1
19	IT-CRA	0 €	1
20	LT-MoA	60.000 €	3
21&22	NL-NVWA (/ELI)	730.000 €	11
23	PT-INRB	47.500 €	6
24	SI-MAE	223.000 €	7
25	ES-INIA	200.000 €	4
1	UK-DEFRA-FERA	912.000 €	6
29	UK-SASA	212.100 €	5
31	Rus. Fed., FGBU-VNIIKR	20.000 €	2
Observer			
	Norway (Bioforsk)	12.000 €	1
	Funds totally decided:	3.607.300 €	
	Funding activities		81

2013 Round of Research Initiation

2013-E-62

Routine test methods for **Monilinia fructicola**

Topic Coordinator: **IT-CRA**; Luca Riccioni; luca.riccioni@entecra.it

2013-F-69

QDETECT follow-up

Topic Coordinator: **UK-DEFRA**; Alan Inman; Alan.Inman@defra.gsi.gov.uk

2013-E-75

IPM strategies against **Drosophilidae** (fruit fly)

Topic Coordinator: **ES-INIA**; Anabel de la Peña; anaisabel.delapena@inia.es

Table 5 - EUPHRESKO II – Participation of partners in 2013 round of research initiation

Partner no.	Partner short name	Total Funds	Total activities
3	AT-AGES	1.000 €	2
6	BE-EV ILVO	40.000 €	2
12	FR-DGAL	60.000 €	2
19	IT-CRA	20.000 €	2
20	LT-MoA	20.000 €	1
21&22	NL-NVWA (/ELI)	0 €*	1
25	ES-INIA	200.000 €	3
27	TR-MARA-GDAR	50.000 €	2
1	UK-DEFRA-FERA	0 €*	1
29	UK-SASA	132.000 €	1
	Funds totally decided:	523.000 €	
	Funding activities		17

*information was not provided in the online tool

Attachments

The following tables provide the information compiled from the EUPHRESKO II request on the actual project status (Status March 2014).

Table 6 - EUPHRESKO II - 2011 Round - Research project status

EUPHRESKO-2 research project status 1st round 07.03.2014											
Topic (no., title, acronym)	Topic coordinator	Project Coordinator	Research providers (no., acronyms)	Total Budget (EURO)	FM (funding mechanism)	Start (dd-mm-yyyy)	duration (month)	proj. manag. inst. (Y/N)	contrac (researcher) (Y/N)	project started (Y/N)	comments (e.g.: interim report delivered, project finalized)
01 - Current and emerging phytophthoras: research supporting risk assessment and risk management (CEP)	Alan Inman (Alan.inman@defra.gsi.gov.uk)	Jeff Peters (Jeff.peters@fera.gsi.gov.uk)	12(-14) (BE-EV-ILVO, EE-PMK, IE-DAFF, IT-CRA, NL-PPS, NO-BIOFORSK, PT-INRB, ES-UPV, UK-FR, UK-Fera, UK-SASA, UK-AFBI (to be confirmed: SI, LT))	467.333.-	NC	01.03.2012	24	Y	Y	Y	
02- Use of novel molecular methods to understand population diversity and its implications on disease management through the use of resistant potato varieties (Potato Cyst Nematode) PCN	Alex Reid (alex.reid@sasa.gsi.gov.uk)	Alex Reid (Alex.Reid@sasa.gsi.gov.uk)	5 (SASA-UK, PPS-NL,ILVO-BE, NAAC-Ukr, NCRD-PL)	107.000.-	NC	01.03.2012	36	Y	Y	Y	Aproximately 50 pallida populations currently going through pot trials to determine virulence. SNP assay designed to differentiate pallida populations which is about to be tested against the Scottish populations. SNP assay will be run against populations from other countries later this year.
03-Development and validation of innovative diagnostic tools for detection and identification of Meloidogyne enterolobii in support of integrated plant protection strategies (MELOID)	Gabriele Schachermayr (gabriele.schachermayr@blw.admin.ch)	Kiewnick Sebastian (Sebastian.kiewnick@acw.admin.ch)	8 (BE-ILVO, JKI-DE, FR-ANSES, CRA-ABP-IT, PPS- NL, MARA-GDAR-BPPRS-TR, FERA-UK, ACW-CH)	175.905.-	NC	01.01.2012	18	Y	Y	Y	project successfully concluded; final report submitted
04-Diagnostic methods for Synchytrium endobioticum, especially for pathotype identification (SENDO)	Alan Inman (Alan.inman@defra.gsi.gov.uk)	Gerard van Leeuwen (NL) and Kirstin Flaff (JKI-DE)	12(-13) (BE-EV-ILVO, BG-BFSA-CLPO, DE-JKI, IE-DAFF, LT-MoA, NL-PPS(+PRI), UK-Fera, UK-SASA, UA-IPP-UAAS, RU-FGU-VNIIKR (PO joining: RO to confirm))	200.486.-	NC	01.03.2012	24	Y	Y	Y	
05- Assessment of the risk posed by ornamentals and tomato seeds infected by Pospiviroids to tomato crops and evaluation of Pospiviroid detection protocols for seed testing in tomato DEP2	Thibaut Olivier (t.olivier@cra.wallonie.be)	Thibaut Olivier (t.olivier@cra.wallonie.be)	8 (CRA-W-BE, ILVO-BE, AGES-AT, CRA-IT, AIS-SI, MAARD-EE, MoA-LT, ANSES-FR)	179.000.-	NC	01.05.2012	24	Y	Y	Y	The annual meeting took place the 19th of June 2013, the final meeting is scheduled for the 3rd of April 2014
06-Epidemiology and diagnosis of potato phytoplasmas and Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum and their contribution to risk management PHYLIB	David Kenyon (david.kenyon@sasa.gsi.gov.uk)	Colin Jeffries (colin.jeffries@sasa.gsi.gov.uk) Jennifer Hodgetts (jennifer.hodgetts@fera.gsi.gov.uk)	11 (SASA-UK, FERA-UK, IVIA-SP, CIMA-CSIC-SP, ILVO-BE, PPI-TR, Univ.-Helsinki-FI, Phytolab-HU: CFIA-Canada, ANSES-FR, INRA-FR, PPS-NL)	525.048.-	NC	01.03.2012	24	Y	Y	Y	Collaborators met after the first year of the project for a 2 day meeting and planning is already started for the final project meeting to coincide with its conclusion late summer 2014.

To above table: EUPHRESKO II - 2011 Round - Research project status

Topic (no., title, acronym)	Topic coordinator	Project Coordinator	Research providers (no., acronyms)	Total Budget (EURO)	FM (funding mechanism)	Start (dd-mm-yyyy)	duration (month)	proj. manag. inst. (Y/N)	contrac (researcher)	project started (Y/N)	comments
07-Epidemiological studies on reservoir hosts and potential vectors of Grapevine flavescence dorée (GFD) and validation of different diagnostic procedures for GFD GRAFDEPI	Sylvia Bluemel (sbluemel@ages.at)	Graziella Pasquini (graziella.pasquini@ente-cra.it)	13 (IT-CRA-PAV, AGES-AT, CRAW-BE, TR-PPRS, PT-INRB, ACW-CH, BE-ILVO, DISTA-IT, DIPROVE-IT, CRA-ABP-IT, IPEP-SB, NIB-SI, IRTA-SP)	213.000.-	mixed NC/VP	01.05.2012	24	Y	Y	Y	Other European laboratories asked to participate to ringtest for FD diagnosis (WP3)
08-Evaluation of factors determining distribution, impact, detection and characterization of apple proliferation and other fruit tree phytoplasmas in the European Community APOPHYT	Silke Steinmüller (silke.steinmoeller@jki.bund.de)	Danilo Christen (danilo.christen@acw.admin.ch)	8 (ACW-CH, AGES-AT, JKI-DE, IT-CRA-PAV, NO-BIOFORSK, BE-CRA-W, CZ-VSUSO, BE-ILVO)	229.000.-	mixed NC/VP	01.11.2012	24	Y	Y	Y	Ongoing, annual report has been sent in January and can be distributed on demand
09-Phytosanitary diagnostic, on-site detection and epidemiology tools for fire blight PHYTFIRE	Sylvia Bluemel (sbluemel@ages.at)	Brion Duffy (brion.duffy@zhaw.ch) Vice-coordinator: Fabio Rezzonico (rezz@zhaw.ch)	14 (ACW-CH, AGES-AT, PPS- NL, INRB-PT, EGE- TR, MARA-GDAR-BPPRS-TR, JKI-DE, TUW- AT, IVIA- ES, FGU VNI IKR- RU, Uzhgorod Univ- UA, UkrNDSKR- UA, PhRL- LT, ARC- EE) + 4 interested partners from SI, FR, IT, BG	554.290.-	mixed NC/VP	01.05.2012	24	Y	Y	Y	http://www.phytfire.org/ Mid-term Report delivered. Final meeting scheduled for 13-15 May 2014 in Cappadocchia, Turkey.
10-Damage potential of Drosophila suzukii and development of phytosanitary measures DROSKII	Silke Steinmüller (silke.steinmoeller@jki.bund.de)	Sauro Simoni (sauro.simoni@entecra.it)	6 (CRA-ABP-IT, JKI-DE, UK-FERA, AGES-AT, ACW-CH, FondMach-IT)	296.143.-	mixed NC/VP	01.09.2012	24	Y	Y	Y	Ongoing, mid-term report has been sent in January and can be distributed on demand

Table 7 - EUPHRESKO II - 2012 Round - Research project status

EUPHRESKO-2 research project status 2nd round 07.03.2014											
Topic (no., title, acronym)	Topic coordinator	Project Coordinator	Research providers (no., acronyms)	Total Budget (EURO)	FM (funding mechanism)	Start (dd-mm-yyyy)	duration (month)	proj. man. inst. (Y/N)	contract (researcher) (Y/N)	project started (Y/N)	comments (e.g.: interim report delivered...)
2 - Risk management and improvement of detection & identification tools for the EC listed Anoplophora species, A. chinensis and A. glabripennis	Silke Steinmoeller (silke.steinmoeller@jki.bund.de)	Ute Hoyer-Tomiczek	3 (JKI-DE, BFW-AT, FERA-UK)	150.000.-	mixed NC/VP	01.04.2013	12 - 24	N	N	y	Work of one partner started, project description not complete yet, waiting for input from one partner
3 - Bursaphelenchus xylophilus methods for early detection	Géraldine Anthoine (geraldine.anthoine@anses.fr)	Géraldine Anthoine (geraldine.anthoine@anses.fr)	4 (ILVO-BE; FR-DGAL; PT-INRB; SI-MAE) + possibly other partners interested	72.500.-	NC	01.09.2013	24	Y	y	y	Kick off meeting organised in october 2013. Many new contributors identified and content of some topics were revised.
5 - The effects of disinfection on Clavibacter michiganensis subsp. sepedonicus and other bacterial pathogens of potato in Europe	Jan Schans (j.schans@minlnv.nl)	Leon Tjou-Tam-Sin (n.n.a.tjou-tam-sin@minlnv.nl)	3 (NL-EL&I, LT-MoA, UK-SASA)	353.000.-	NC	01.04.2013	24	N	N	Y	project in progress
8-Determination of specificity and test performance study of current and novel molecular methods for Ralstonia solanacearum (brown rot of potatoes) and identification of methods allowing for detection of non-European strains of brown rot	Jan Schans (j.schans@minlnv.nl)	Leon Tjou-Tam-Sin (n.n.a.tjou-tam-sin@minlnv.nl)	4 (BE-ILVO, NL-EL&I, UK-FERA, SI-MoA)	61.000.-	NC	01.07.2013	24	N	N	Y	project in progress
10 - Diagnostics and risk management for plant health threats in wood chips and bark for bio-energy imported from other continents	Steen Lykke Nielsen (SteenL.Nielsen@agrsci.dk)	Mogens Nicolaisen (mogens.nicolaisen@agrsci.dk)	DASTI-DK, DEFRA-UK	450.-	VP	02.10.2013	24	N	N	N	Project started 01.01.2014 and closes 31.12.2015
11 - Assessment of Dickeya and Pectobacterium spp. on potatoes and ornamentals	Jan Schans (j.schans@minlnv.nl)	Maria Bergsma-Vlami (m2.bergsma@minlnv.nl)	7 (BE-ILVO, LT-MoA, NL-EL&I, NO-Bioforsk, SI-MAFF, UK-FERA and UK-SASA)	260.000.-	NC	01.01.2013	24	N	N	Y	project in progress
13 - Epirix (flea beetle) species, life cycles and detection method	Steen Lykke Nielsen (SteenL.Nielsen@agrsci.dk)	Not appointed yet	DASTI-DK, INRB-PT, FERA-UK, DGAI-F, SASA-SC, NVWA-NL	445.000.-	Mixed NC/VP	02.10.2013	36	N	N	N	Problems to handle the mixed funding mechanisms
16 - Grapevine flavescence dorée (FD) follow up Vitisens,GRAFDEPI and Qdetect)	Jana Erjavec (Jana.Erjavec@gov.si)	Not appointed yet (NIB)	3 (SI-MAE, AT-AGES, IT-CRA)	60.000.-	mixed NC/VP	01.10.2013 (or 01.2014)	24	N	N	N	
19 - Monochamus spp., insect vectors of Bursaphelenchus xylophilus	Steen Lykke Nielsen (SteenL.Nielsen@agrsci.dk)	Not appointed yet	DASTI-DK, SI-MAE, Slovenia, ILVO, Belgium, INRB, Portugal, NVWA, Netherlands	300.000.-	Mixed NC/VP	02.10.2013	36	N	N	N	Problems to handle the mixed funding mechanisms
24 - Plant Health Fellowship	Alan Inman (Alan.Inman@defra.gov.uk)	As per winning bid	As per winning bid	600.000	RP	01.09.2013	36	Y	N	N	

To above table: EUPHRESKO II - 2012 Round - Research project status

Topic (no., title, acronym)	Topic coordinator	Project Coordinator	Research providers (no., acronyms)	Total Budget (EURO)	FM (funding mechanism)	Start (dd-mm-yyyy)	duration (month)	proj. man. inst. (Y/N)	contract (researcher) (Y/N)	project started (Y/N)	comments
25 - Establishing the basis for an International Plant Sentinel Network as an early-warning system for future pest threats	Alan Inman (Alan.Inman@defra.gov.uk)	Elie Barham (BGCI) with Charles Lane (Fera): ellie.barham@bgci.org; charles.lane@fera.gov.uk	Fera-UK, JKI-DE, PPS-NL, DIBAF-IT (with subcontracts to: BGCI; CABI; and Forest Research (UK))	402.603	NC	01.04.2013	36	N	N	N	
26 - Population dynamics of <i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i> an <i>M. fallax</i>	Jan Schans (j.schans@minlnv.nl)	Loes den Nijs (l.j.m.f.den.nijs@minlnv.nl)	4 (NL-EL&I, BE-ILVO, FR-DGAL and SI-MAFF)	75.000.-	NC	01.05.2013	24	Y	Y	Y	project in progress
28 - Development and harmonization of methods for diagnosis, detection and identification of <i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>Actinidiae</i>	Alberto Masci (a.masci@mpaaf.gov.it)	Massimo Pilotti and Stefania Loreti (massimo.pilotti@entecra.it; stefania.lorete@entecra.it)	5 (IT-CRA-PAV; FR – Anses LSV; ES-INIA; PT-INRB; NZ - MPI-PHEL)	90.000.-	NC	01.05.2013	24	Y	Y	Y	we experienced some problems in finding the project coordinator(s), so the process is a bit delayed.
29 - Reference collection for regulated viruses and viroids	Jan Schans (j.schans@minlnv.nl)	Annelien Roenhorst (j.w.roenhorst@minlnv.nl)	3 (AT-AGES, DE-JKI, NL-EL&I and UK-SASA)	300.000.-	NC	01.11.2013	24	Y	Y	Y	project in progress; kick-off-meeting June 2015
32- Assessment and testing of strawberry pathogens	Küllli Kaare (kylli.kaare@agri.ee)	Evelin Loit (evelin.loit@emu.ee)	7 (BMLFUW-AT, AGES-AT, MARDD-EST, DAFF-IR, MoA-EL&I -NL, INIA-ESP, FGU VNIIKR -RUS)	227.700.-	mixed NC/VP	15.07.2013	24	Y	Y	Y	Project started 15.07.2013. Due to job changes of partners there was some problems to have/find contact person. Kick-Off meeting 12.09.2013
36 - Validation of QBOL Barcoding protocols by end-users	Alan Inman (Alan.Inman@defra.gov.uk)	Bart van de Vossenber (b.t.l.h.van.de.vossenber@minlnv.nl)	FERA-UK, AGES-AT, ILVO-BE, ANSES-FR, JKI-DE, INIA-ES, PPS-NL, NIB-SI	135.000.-	NC	01.09.2013	12	Y	Y	Y	Kick-Off meeting Febr./March 2014
37- Rapid diagnostics of <i>Xanthomonas arboricola</i> pv. <i>pruni</i> (Xap): development and validation of methodologies for discrimination between Xap isolates and look-a-likes	Jan Schans (j.schans@minlnv.nl)	Maria Bergsma-Vlami (m2.bergsma@minlnv.nl)	4 (AT-AGES,BMLFUW-AT, NL-EL&I, ES-INIA)	165.000.-	NC	01.09.2013	24	Y	Y	Y	project in progress, final meeting 2015

Table 8 - EUPHRESKO II - 2013 Round - Research project status

EUPHRESKO-2 research project status 3rd round 07.03.2014											
Topic (no., title, acronym)	Topic coordinator	Project Coordinator	Research providers (no., acronyms)	Total Budget (EURO)	FM (funding mechanism)	Start (dd-mm-yyyy)	duration (month)	proj. manangement installed (Y/N)	contract (resea-cher) (Y/N)	project started (Y/N)	comments (e.g.: interim report delivered...)
2013-E-62 - Development and validation of molecular tools for detection and identification of European <i>Monilinia</i> species - DIMO	luca.riccioni@entecra.it	Antonieta De Cal (INIA, ES)	5 (TR-GDAR, ES-INIA, IT-CRA, LT-MoA, F-DGAL,6. ES-IRTA)	155.000.-	NC	01.07.2014	24	N	N	N	Work plan, Contracts and LoCs in preparation
2013-F-69 - QDETECT follow-up	Alan.Inman@defra.gsi.gov.uk	Neil Boonham (Fera) - neil.boonham@fera.gsi.gov.uk	8 (UK-DEFRA; BE-ILVO; UK-SASA; DK-DASTI, AT-AGES; AT-BMLFUW?; NL-EL&I; ES-INIA; F-DGAL)	237.500.-	mixed NC/VP	01.09.2014	24	N	N	N	
2013-E-75 - IPM strategies against Drosophilidae (fruit fly)	anaisabel.delapena@inia.es	Ismael Sánchez Ramos	5 (ES-INIA; TR-GDAR, AT-AGES; IT-CRA; BE-ILVO)	130.000.-	NC	01.07.2014	24	N	N	N	Work plan, Contracts and LoCs in preparation/progress